

Name of activity: Reflection workshop “Beliefs about equity, inclusion and social justice in initial teacher education”.

Aimed at: Community of teacher educators.

Author: Mirko Aguilar- Valdés (Universidad Católica del Maule, Chile)

Presentation:

According to the Teacher Educators' Diversity-Responsive Practices (TE-DIP) framework presented by Ponet et al. (2025), teacher educators play a key role in ensuring that future teachers promote equity, diversity and social justice in the classroom. Specifically, equity is defined as ensuring fair learning conditions and opportunities for all. Diversity is conceived as the ability to include cultural, social, gender, origin and life experience differences, which requires teaching practices that are sensitive to the plurality of identities and contexts. Finally, social justice is proposed as a guiding principle that directs teaching practices towards reducing systemic inequalities, promoting the inclusion of historically marginalised perspectives and encouraging the transformation of oppressive structures.

In order to advance the development of strategies that address these issues, the same authors point out that questioning the reference frameworks themselves is essential for the teaching practices used by teacher educators to move forward in this direction. In other words, challenging the beliefs and assumptions that implicitly guide teaching practice promotes the modelling of equitable, inclusive and socially just practices during the education of pre-service teachers.

Based on this idea, the present proposal suggests the need to analyse how personal beliefs influence the way educators address these issues in the classroom. To this end, and as proposed by the InFo-TED network, this proposal assumes that teacher educators have good and different reasons for doing what they do in the classroom. However, it also warns of the need to review the assumptions that tacitly limit or favour the implementation of equitable, inclusive and socially just practices.

Theoretical background:

According to Pajares (1992), beliefs are deeply rooted cognitive structures that are personal, affective and experiential in nature. In the field of education, beliefs act as a filter for teachers, guiding their decision-making and promoting or limiting the adoption of inclusive strategies.

On the other hand, reflective practice has been positioned as an exercise that allows for the investigation and analysis of personal beliefs. According to Schon (1983), reflection on action allows for retrospective review of the implicit assumptions underlying classroom decisions, consciously questioning the scope of one's own practice.

In this context, the creation of a reflective space around beliefs offers the possibility of analysing one's own teaching practice, listening to alternative interpretations and promoting its transformation within the framework of shared work with others. According to Ping et al. (2018), the establishment of a space for dialogue between teacher educators, such as learning communities, represents an excellent opportunity to promote their learning and professional development.

Aim:

To promote a process of analysis of teacher educators' beliefs regarding equity, diversity and social justice in the initial teacher education classroom, using the parable of 'The Chained Elephant' as a catalyst, which allows us to understand how past teaching experiences can limit the implementation of actions aimed at promoting these three key concepts.

Activity (90 minutes)

Step 1: Read the parable (individually). Each participant is given a copy of Jorge Bucay's story, 'The Chained Elephant' (5 minutes).

The Chained Elephant (Jorge Bucay)

When I was little, I loved circuses. What I liked most about circuses were the animals, and the animal that impressed me most was the elephant. I was fascinated by its enormous size and tremendous strength.

However, after the performance and until shortly before returning to the stage, the elephant always remained tied to a small stake driven into the ground with a chain that imprisoned one of its legs. The chain was thick, but the stake was a tiny piece of wood driven a few centimetres into the ground. It seemed obvious to me that an animal capable of uprooting a tree with its strength could also pull on that tiny stake and free itself. That mystery still seems obvious to me. What holds it back? Why doesn't it run away?

After asking my teachers and relatives whom I considered wise, the answer some gave me was: "The elephant didn't run away because it was trained". I then asked the obvious question, "If it was trained, why was it chained?". The truth is that I don't remember receiving any coherent answer, until someone who turned out to be wise enough gave me a convincing answer: 'The circus elephant didn't run away because it had been tied to a similar stake since it was very young.'

I closed my eyes and imagined the helpless newborn elephant tied to the stake. I'm sure that at that moment the little animal pulled and pulled, trying to free itself. It must have ended the day exhausted because that stake was stronger than it was. Day after day, it must have tried

again with the same result. And so it went until one terrible day for the rest of its life, the elephant accepted its helplessness and resigned itself to its fate.

That powerful elephant does not escape because it believes it cannot; it has engraved in its memory the helplessness it felt as a youngster. And the worst thing is that it never tested its strength again. Often, people experience the same thing as the circus elephant; we live chained to hundreds of stakes that take away our freedom. We think we “can't” do a number of things simply because one day, a long time ago, we tried and failed and/or because someone told us we wouldn't be able to do it. So we engraved this message in our memory: “I can't and I never will be able to”.

We have grown up carrying this self-imposed message and that is why we never tried to free ourselves from the stake again. When we sometimes feel the shackles and rattle the chains, we glance sideways at the stake and think, I can't and I never will. Surely we are stronger and better prepared now, but that memory holds us back when it comes to trying to free ourselves.

Step 2: Initial dialogue (in groups): A brief round of conversation begins with guided questions that allow each person to share their interpretation of the parable (10 minutes).

Guiding questions:

1. What element of the story had the greatest impact on you?
2. What does the elephant represent?
3. What does the small stake symbolise? And the chain?
4. What is the meaning of the story?

Step 3: Belief mapping* (in groups): Each participant is asked to describe and link a personal experience based on the parable and identify those ‘stakes’ that lead them to engage in socially inequitable, non-inclusive or unfair behaviour in the classroom because their belief tells them that ‘it won't work any other way,’ despite having doubts or indications that it could be improved (20 minutes).

*According to Pajares (1992), the exercise of identifying a belief can be complex, but there are some criteria that allow us to distinguish it. First, the belief is associated with a significant and emotionally intense personal experience. Second, it is subjective in nature and involves an evaluative judgement about what is desirable or appropriate. And third, it is not based on logical or empirical evidence. Beliefs do not constitute a formal or validated theory, and are not necessarily shared knowledge.

Guiding questions:

1. What is its origin?
2. Was there an experience of failure or an observation in the past (the 'stake') that cemented it?
3. What emotion or feeling did you experience at that time? Can you perceive if that same emotion still manifests itself in your practice when you face similar situations?
4. Could you identify a practice that you maintain simply out of inertia, without having questioned it in years, because your belief tells you that 'it won't work any other way'?

Step 4: Challenging inertia (in a group): When listening to colleagues' narratives, a educator may see their own struggles, fears and biases reflected, but they can also contrast their experience with other perspectives. Considering the shared experiences, the task now is to transform the individual reflection process into a shared reflection, establishing a support network that encourages challenging these beliefs. To do this, participants ask their peers questions that invite them to question their beliefs (20 minutes).

Guiding questions:

1. How does that belief manifest itself in your daily practice?
2. If you had to defend that belief to a group of colleagues, what current evidence do you have to support it, beyond the initial experience that gave rise to it?
3. If that belief is protecting you from something, what could it be? What risks or discomforts might you be avoiding by holding on to it?
4. Thinking about the students you teach, how might that belief be affecting the type of support you offer them or the challenges you set for them? What model of inclusion and equity are you sharing with pre-service teachers?

Step 5: Proposal for a new attempt (in a group). Group members share an idea or action strategy that they could implement in the classroom to challenge their limiting belief (20 minutes).

Guiding questions:

1. If you had to "pull up the stakes" today, what would you do differently?
2. Thinking about your next class, what change could you make to test, even in a small way, whether your belief holds up in current practice?

Step 6: Closing the Activity (plenary): Teacher educators are encouraged to share their reflections on the activity. You can conclude with a final comment on the importance of systematic and

collaborative reflection as a mechanism to prevent our past experiences from becoming “stakes” or limiting beliefs. Similarly, they are invited to continue this process of self-analysis, recognising that, like the adult elephant, time, context and possibilities are constantly changing, so it is worth trying again (15 minutes).